

Weed composition in dry seeded wetland rice

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A major constraint on rice yields in Orissa State is high weed incidence. We identified the major weed flora and their composition in rainfed lowland rice during the 1987 wet season. All weeds in 0.25-m² samples from 12 wetland ricefields (two samples/field), were identified and the weed species found in all samples counted. All fields had been dry seeded.

Echinochloa colona was the dominant grassy weed found (see table). Sedges *Cyperus iria*, *C. difformis*, *Fimbristylis miliacea*, and *Scirpus articulatus* also had high incidence. Among the broadleaf weeds, *Cyanotis cucullata* and *Ludwigia parviflora* were high. *Ipomoea aquatica*, *Hedyotis corymbosa*, and *Portulaca oleracea* appeared at later crop growth stages. ■

First appearance and floristic composition of weeds in Orissa State, India.^a

Botanical name	First appearance (DARE)	Weed composition ^b			
		30 DARE		At harvest (165 DARE)	
		Plants/m ^{2b}	% of population	Plants/m ²	% of population
<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	15	10.80	1.49	33.60	4.24
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	15	145.60	20.17	76.80	9.69
<i>Leptochloa chinensis</i> (L.) Nees	15	32.20	4.46	21.20	2.67
<i>Ischaemum rugosum</i> Salisb.	30	27.20	3.77	27.20	3.43
<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	15	44.80	6.21	69.20	8.73
<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	15	158.80	21.99	51.20	6.46
<i>C. difformis</i> L.	30	37.60	5.21	40.40	5.10
<i>C. rotundus</i> L.	30	18.40	2.55	21.20	2.67
<i>C. imbricatus</i> Retz	30	9.60	1.33	24.00	3.03
<i>Fimbristylis miliacea</i> (L.) Vahl	15	73.60	10.19	47.12	5.95
<i>Scirpus acutus</i> Muhl.	30	20.00	2.77	32.00	4.04
<i>S. articulatus</i> L.	30	34.68	4.80	54.40	6.86
<i>Aeschynomene indica</i> L.	15	10.40	1.44	22.80	2.88
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R. Br.	30	6.80	0.94	17.32	2.19
<i>Cyanotis cucullata</i> Kunth	15	32.00	4.43	78.80	9.94
<i>Hedyotis corymbosa</i> (L.) Lam.	75	-	-	17.20	2.17
<i>Ipomoea aquatica</i> Forssk	90	-	-	20.72	2.61
<i>Limnophila indica</i> (L.) Druce	30	6.80	0.94	12.00	1.51
<i>Ludwigia parviflora</i> (L.) Roxb.	30	22.72	3.15	50.40	6.36
<i>Marsilea quadrifolia</i> L.	30	14.80	2.05	-	-
<i>Manachoria vaginalis</i> (Burm. f.) Presl.	30	5.72	0.80	11.52	1.45
<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> L.	120	-	-	18.72	2.36
<i>Sesbania exaltata</i> (Raf.) Cory.	30	4.28	0.59	14.80	1.87
<i>Sphenoclea zeylanica</i> Gaertn.	30	5.20	0.72	30.00	3.79
Total		722.00	100.00	792.60	100.00

^aDARE = days after rice emergence. ^bAv of 24 samples.

Farming systems

Intercropping following rice

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In the Cauvery Delta Zone, cotton *Gossypium hirsutum* or black gram *Vigna mungo* is grown in Jan-Feb following wet season rice. We evaluated cotton MCU7, soybean *Glycine max* (CO 1), and black gram (ADT4) as pure crops and cotton

intercropped with black gram or soybean, in a randomized block design with four replications.

Soil was clay (fine Udic Chromusterts) with CEC 35 meq/100 g soil, 0.5% organic C, and 65% water-holding capacity. Spacing was 60 × 30 cm for cotton and 30 × 10 cm for black gram and soybean. In the intercrop treatments, two rows of cotton were sown at 45/75 × 30-cm spacing and two rows of the intercrop at 75- × 30-cm spacing.

Cotton was irrigated six times, with 30 cm water total; the pulse crops were

irrigated twice with 10 cm water total. The water table was 6.7 m deep during the cropping period.

Yield of cotton in the paired row intercrop with black gram equaled yield of cotton as a pure crop (see table). Cotton + black gram gave the highest net return. ■

Rice-based cropping systems for rainfed lowland conditions

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We studied the effect of seeding and fertilizer rates on the production potential of rice-based cropping systems under rainfed lowland conditions in 1988-89.

The soil was silty loam with pH 8.4, 0.62% organic C, and 278-39.2-140.2 kg available N, P₂O₅, and K₂O per hectare.

Radha rice (35-d-old seedlings) was transplanted 15 Jul and harvested 10 Dec 1988. Gram C235, linseed Subhra, and lentil Pant 406 were broadcast 25 Nov in

Yield and net return of sole crops and intercrops in rice fallow system. TRRI, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India, 1988.

Treatment	Yield ^a (t/ha)			Yield value ^b (\$/ha)	Cultivation cost (\$/ha)	Net return (\$/ha)
	Cotton	Soybean	Black gram			
Cotton	1.1	-	-	571	264	307
Soybean	-	1.4	-	363	112	251
Black gram	-	-	1.3	625	131	494
Cotton + soybean	0.8	1.2	-	726	343	383
Cotton + black gram	1.1	-	1.0	1052	336	716
LSD (P = 0.05)	-	-	-	-	-	18

^aMean of 4 replications. ^bCotton, \$519/t; soybean, \$259/t; black gram, \$481/t.

the standing rice crop at two seeding rates (normal and 50% higher than normal) with and without fertilizer. Fertilizer was broadcast 3 d before sowing the intercrop. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with four replications.

Rice yield was 3.8 t/ha. Yields of gram, linseed, and lentil ranged from 0.12 to 0.17, 0.45 to 0.68, and 0.16 to 0.29 t/ha, respectively. (Lower yields of gram and linseed were due to a winter drought.)

Rice - linseed produced significantly higher rice equivalency yield than rice - gram and rice - lentil (see table). Linseed with fertilizer yielded significantly higher than other crops. The interaction between crops and seeding rates was not significant. ■

Productivity of rice-based intercropping systems in Pusa, Bihar, India, 1988-89.

Treatment	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Rice	Intercrop	Rice yield Equivalence
Rice alone	3.7	-	3.7
Rice + gram, normal seeding rate, no fertilizer (S ₁ F ₁)	3.7	0.1	4.1
Rice + gram, normal seeding rate, fertilized ^a (S ₁ F ₂)	3.7	0.2	4.2
Rice + gram + 150% seeding, no fertilizer (S ₂ F ₁)	3.7	0.1	4.1
Rice + gram + 150% seeding, fertilized (S ₂ F ₂)	3.8	0.2	4.2
Rice + linseed + S ₁ F ₁	3.7	0.4	4.5
Rice + linseed + S ₁ F ₂	3.7	0.6	4.9
Rice + linseed + S ₂ F ₁	3.7	0.6	4.8
Rice + linseed + S ₂ F ₂	3.8	0.7	5.1
Rice + lentil + S ₁ F ₁	3.7	0.2	4.3
Rice + lentil + S ₁ F ₂	3.7	0.2	4.2
Rice + lentil + S ₂ F ₁	3.6	0.2	4.2
Rice + lentil + S ₂ F ₂	3.7	0.3	4.4
LSD (0.05)	ns	0.1	0.4

^a20 kg N + 18 kg P/ha for gram and lentil, 30 kg N + 9 kg P/ha for linseed.

Production potential and economics of upland rice + pigeonpea

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Upland rice + pigeonpea is the widely adopted mixed cropping system in Keonjhar. But grazing by stray cattle after rice harvest reduces pigeonpea yields. Pigeonpea remains in the field 2 mo longer, and farmers lose interest in protecting a thinly populated crop that may not give an adequate return. Recommended seeding rates for single crop rice and pigeonpea are 100 and 20 kg/ha, respectively.

We evaluated proportions of rice and pigeonpea during 1985-87 wet season. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Experimental crop schedules are given in the table.

Soil of the experimental site was sandy with pH 5.7, low available N (242 kg/ha) and P (8.0 kg/ha), and medium available K (97.0 kg/ha).

Rice cultivar Shankar (85 d duration) and pigeonpea UPAS 120 (145 d) were sown 21 Jun 1985, 24 Jun 1986, and 27 Jun 1987. Fertilizer was 60-13-25 kg NPK/ha for rice and 20-17.4-0 kg NPK/ha for pigeonpea.

Line sowing 2 rows of pigeonpea 50 cm apart after each 10 rows of rice 15 cm apart gave the highest return. ■

Yield and economics of rice + pigeonpea cropping system under different sowing methods and mixing proportions.^a Orissa, India, 1985-87.

Treatment		Yield (t/ha)	Gross return (\$/ha)	Profit (\$/ha)
Sowing	Proportion			
Rice and pigeonpea mixed and broadcast	Rice 60% + pigeonpea 40%	1.2 1.2	506.44	342.81
	Rice 70% + pigeonpea 30%	1.5 1.0	463.38	297.38
	Rice 80% + pigeonpea 20%	1.6 0.9	444.88	276.56
	Rice 60% (1.5 m broadcast sown) + pigeonpea 40% (2 rows 50 cm apart)	1.3 1.4	565.81	399.75
Rice broadcast and pigeonpea line dibbled	Rice 70% (3.0 m broadcast sown) + pigeonpea 30% (2 rows 50 cm apart)	1.6 1.2	539.63	371.50
	Rice 80% (4.5 m broadcast sown) + pigeonpea 20% (2 rows 50 cm apart)	1.9 1.0	494.75	323.94
	Rice 60% (10 rows 15 cm apart) + pigeonpea 40% (2 rows 50 cm apart)	1.5 1.5	626.44	458.44
Rice and pigeonpea line sown	Rice 70% (20 rows 15 cm apart) + pigeonpea 30% (2 rows 50 cm apart)	1.6 1.3	599.31	418.69
	Rice 80% (30 rows 15 cm apart) + pigeonpea 20% (2 rows 50 cm apart)	2.1 1.1	563.00	391.63

^aAv of 2 yr.